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**D AS PART OF THE MODERNIZATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL
K EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN, HIGHER
EDUCATION WAYS TO CREATE A COLLABORATIVE DIGITAL
EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

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Annotation. The Head of State has inscribed the concept of "fair Kazakhstan-an honest citizen-an advanced nation" into the future vision of an independent country, therefore, in order to form an advanced contemplative citizen in the new Kazakhstan, we must prepare future specialists with high professional qualifications and innovation, working in good

qualifications and innovations working in good conditions will create a training, technology model of practical training, education, training, personnel, pedagogical, profession, employer requirements, professional competence

Аннотация Глава государства вписал концепцию "справедливый Казахстан - честный гражданин - передовая нация" в видение будущего независимой страны, поэтому, чтобы сформировать продвинутого созерцательного гражданина в новом Казахстане, мы должны подготовить будущих специалистов с высокой профессиональной квалификацией и инновациями, работающих в хороших условиях. вера.

Ключевые слова: квалификацией и инновациями, работающих в хороших условиях создат подготовка, профессиональная компетентность.

At the third meeting of the National Kurultai, the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan K. Zh.-Tokayev separately focused on the basic values that define the new face of the nation: "we must continue to instill this fundamental value in the minds of generations. An honest citizen is someone who has good qualities, works hard and achieves success in an honest way. That is, honesty and Justice are above

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI

all. To be an advanced nation, the whole society must change its consciousness and establish new values. If every person deserves the title of "honest citizen", a just society will be established in the country. "An honest man-honest work-honest success" are inseparable concepts. These three pillars can be called the main key to becoming an advanced and successful country."[1]

The Head of State has inscribed the concept of "fair Kazakhstan-an honest citizen-an advanced nation" into the future vision of an independent country, therefore, in order to form an advanced contemplative citizen in the new Kazakhstan, we must prepare future specialists with high professional qualifications and innovation, working in good faith.

The dynamic development of digital technologies at the beginning of the XXI century has become a global trend in the development of mankind, the process of informatization, which is taking place in society at a rapid pace, has increased the scope of digital technologies, and this trend has strengthened the requirements for the digital competence of teachers in the conditions of digital Kazakhstan.

Today, the indicators of global competitiveness of any state are determined by the development of digital technologies in this country, the labor market and employers compare the requirements of future specialists to master digital competencies along with professional competencies.

Within the framework of the AP19680242 project "creation of a collaborative digital educational environment of higher educational institutions as part of the modernization of the pedagogical education system in the Republic of Kazakhstan", large-scale work was carried out on the scientific and (or) scientific and technical grant financing of the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2023-2025 on the formation of digital competencies of future teachers in the 2023-2024 academic year.

In order to study the theoretical and methodological, innovative, technological and linear methodological aspects of the formation of a digital educational environment in the system of collaborative pedagogical education, modernization of the pedagogical education system in Kazakhstan, formation of a collaborative digital

educational environment of the university, M. H. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, I. Zhansugurov Zhetysu University, Kokshetau University named after. Sh. Walikhanov collaborative pedagogical consortium has been established and a cooperation agreement has been concluded.

The result of the joint activity of a teacher and students, the choice of learning technology depends on many factors, according to the research of scientist E. S. Polat, a teacher formed digital competence can easily perform such roles as moderator, tutor, facilitator, [2].

A number of researchers consider collaboration as a synonym for the concepts of "association", "cooperation", "partnership" and apply it in parallel with the term "cooperation" to combine the concepts of "joint activity", "joint activity", "group form of interaction organization", "cooperation in education" [3].

A.V. Kulikov: "Collaboration is the philosophy of education, the initial concept of joint activity, learning and professional-academic interaction" - he notes that cooperation in the educational environment is even wider [4].

And G.P. Based on the research of Sinitsyna, collaboration is one of the components of the educational strategy of collective learning [5].

Collaborative pedagogical cooperation means the collective nature of activities based on the synergy of resources, competences and creative abilities of the subjects in interaction:

- 1) Heterarchical process of allocation of educational tasks; synergy of competence and creative abilities of learners;
- 2) 2) self-organization of "Learning communities"; lack of strict rules of interaction;
- 3) 3) Variety of interactions in study groups during the performance of study tasks;
- 4) 4) The product of the educational activity differs from the goal of education: it is impossible to accurately predict in advance;
- 5) 5) Network nature of interaction and communication of subjects of the educational process;
- 6) 6) The assistant role of the teacher, the ability to organize educational activities in various directions in order to increase the interests of learners [6].

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI

In the proposed project, within the framework of the modernization of the pedagogical education system in the Republic of Kazakhstan, Kazakhstan universities jointly organized online and offline seminars, conferences and forums, methodological seminars, webinars, coaching sessions in schools to create a collaborative digital educational environment of higher educational institutions; an online presentation of the scientific works prepared by the scientists of higher education institutions joining the consortium was made, a pedagogical conference was held, the contribution of each higher education institution was determined and the quality was evaluated (Table 1).

Advantages of using digital platforms:

- 1) Teaching opportunities for digital communication with students and colleagues;
- 2) Developing skills to exchange and create materials with teachers in a digital environment;
- 3) Using digital content to create educational material and adapt existing content;
- 4) Deepening of knowledge about methods of information protection;
- 5) Assessment of reliability of information and identification of false or biased information;
- 6) Safe and responsible use of digital technologies;
- 7) Creative use of digital technologies to solve educational problems;
- 8) Use of digital technologies in the educational process and control of online activity of learners;
- 9) Learning to use digital tools to evaluate and control the progress and intellectual growth levels of students and their application [7].

Within the framework of the modernization of the pedagogical education system in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the theoretical-methodological, innovative-technological and network methodological foundations of the formation of a collaborative digital educational environment of higher educational institutions were defined and the pedagogical education portal <https://edu-collaboration.kz/> was opened.

**MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR
XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI**

Table 1 – Priority areas of conducted activities

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	International Forum "University-school collaboration: innovation, technology and methodology" /Openings of the international forum: "Dulati pedagogical class" was opened within the framework of the scientific project	
	"Formation of digital competences of teachers in the collaborative digital education environment of UNIVERSITY-SCHOOL: theory and methodology" republican webinar / cooperation of Dulati University with general secondary schools	
	Collaborative scientific research has started between scientists of Dulati University and Marmara University (Turkey).	HYPERLINK " https://dulaty.kz/2020-01-30-02-50-58/item/5805-dulati-universiteti-men-marmara-universiteti-alymdaryny-arysynda-kollaborativti-ylymi "

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA XALQARO TAJRIBALAR VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR XALQARO ILMIIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI

The pedagogical education portal <https://edu-collaboration.kz/> is intended for students of a higher pedagogical educational institution studying in the pedagogical profession.

The purpose of the pedagogical education portal is to form a systematic approach of future teachers to their professional activities; improvement of preparation for self-education of future teachers; effective use of digital technologies in the educational process for the future teacher; formation of cognitive activities and informational, creative competences and digital-creative competences of future teachers.

The main menu of the pedagogical education portal <https://edu-collaboration.kz/> consists of 4 blocks: "About Us" block; "About the project" blog; "Communication" block; Block "News" (Figure 1).

Figure 1 is the home page of the pedagogical education portal <https://edu-collaboration.kz/>

In the "Gallery" block of the pedagogical education portal, there are colorful pictures containing videos informing about the activities carried out under the Project (Figure 2).

The pedagogical education portal <https://edu-collaboration.kz/> introduces future teachers to the intricacies of the pedagogical process in the digital environment, forms a systematic approach to their professional activities and

professionally important personal qualities of future teachers; the future teacher gets acquainted with the types and intricacies of digital platforms, learns digital technologies.

Advantages of the proposed Project:

First, to concentrate the scientific and intellectual potential resources of Kazakh higher education institutions in one channel, and the eminent scientists of higher education institutions will join forces to jointly and qualitatively prepare digital teaching content of available subjects.

Secondly, there is an opportunity to share digital educational contents of a qualitatively prepared subject (textbook, teaching-methodical tools, pedagogical cases, electronic portfolio, diaries of pedagogical practice, etc.). And this, in turn, ensures high-quality, meaningful preparation of digital educational content of subjects and prevents unauthorized copying of the obtained results.

Thirdly, it leads to revitalization of internal and external academic mobility in Kazakhstan universities.

Fourthly, a wide path will be opened to learn, research, use and promote innovative practices of Kazakh higher education institutions in cooperation.

Fifthly, the collaborative research of scientists of Kazakhstan universities makes a significant contribution to the improvement of the quality of pedagogical education and increases the competitiveness of universities.

Figure 2 – "News" blog of the pedagogical education portal <https://edu-collaboration.kz/>

In order to turn education into the central generation of the new model of economic growth in the 21st century, in which there is a need to form, create and improve a collaborative digital educational environment of higher educational institutions within the framework of the modernization of the pedagogical education system, it is necessary to direct the training program to the development of critical thinking and independent research skills.

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